

Narrative A: Brother Jerry Realm Episode 1

Location of experience: Windcrest, Texas

This is the first of the experiences on January 18, 2024, time of episode 2:20Pm to 2:55Pm

I was sitting on the side of my bed watching TV between packing and sorting my bedroom for a move. I was sitting on my bed sorting a pile of clothes from the dresser drawers and looking up I literally saw a tall slit of light from floor to ceiling in front of me and in front of my dresser with the tv sitting on it, maybe 5 feet from me, like a door opened about 3" wide and could see the bright day light and green leaves moving like from a breeze towards the top portion of the opening. Could see a vague outline of an actual door at an angle and the thickness of the door itself which was about 1-1.5" thick and it was floor to ceiling also.

Out of nowhere, I was there in a house I was not familiar with, it had an arched doorway in a kitchen, saw an electric stove, a coffee maker with the red light on and about ¼ of a pot left in the carafe. A toaster with crumbs on the top and a few on the countertop. No idea where I was, but heard my name called out "Mittie Dee" and my heart dropped into my stomach, there was only one person ever to call me that, I turned around and saw my brother Jerry, standing there smiling, he had on a slightly faded soft plaid burgundy shirt with the third button edge chipped, a pocket the left breast with the sleeves rolled up about mid forearm and old faded Levi jeans with stringy bottom edge hems and brown old tattered boat deck shoes, and we both hugged and could feel his beard scratching on my forehead and getting tangled in my hair, he put his arm around me, I fit under, I told him your totally white headed, last time I saw you had the pretty salt and pepper hair and beard! he said life has a wickedness to it for some more than others. "I need to show and tell you some things you should know".

He grabbed my left hand and led me to a bedroom almost across from the kitchen, in that room was two small windows above the longer ones with cream colored roman cloth shades that did not cover the top smaller of the windows. with light coming into the room, a dark brown ceiling fan with dusty blades and 2 chains hanging, a hospital bed at about 90 degree with my brother Jerry in it about center of the room, but yet he was standing beside me!!!! There was a rolling bed tray they use in hospitals for patients to eat from in bed or treatments on the left side of the bed towards the feet area

The emotional feeling in that room was cold, sad, fear, the smell was someone had cooked or eaten chili in that room very recent, Jerry said "Mit, I am so sorry for not seeing you sooner, Tiger wronged you again" and then squeezed my hand and he teared up (he had the most lovely green eyes I had ever seen before). He said, "Please watch this." It was like an 8mm camera that my dad had used recording us growing up.

When the “movie “started. It was like an old drive in theater that engulfed the room and it just appeared with Jerry in the hospital bed at 90-degree angle, our cousin Carol you could hear her bizarre laugh and her rrrrrriiiiiiggghhhhtttt! famous comment in the background. No overhead light on and getting dark outside by the way the light was fading coming the through top small windows, she walked in the room and turned light on with a drink in a cup, a white Styrofoam along with a red long plastic spoon sticking up out of the cup and asked him if he wanted some and proceeded to give him with a spoon, she sat on the side of the bed spoon feeding him. Looked like possibly a chocolate shake and he ate about half the container, and she pushed the table across his waist to place arms on, and took drink out and left, you could hear her talking to Tiger and Jan in a different room. His facial expression and skin color changed (massive distress) and he grabbed the table and was trying to yell for help, he was leaning to left of the bed with legs crossed at the ankles and no side rail up, the sheer panic that was consuming him, he fell out of the bed onto the floor and was laying on his left side with a big old scar to his right knee half-moon shaped, there with legs still crossed at the ankles and then you see his head on the floor his eyes open and like it zoomed in and 3 set of feet appeared , one wearing scuff house shoes(dark blue and cream in color), dark brown oxford like ladies shoes, and deck shoes a medium gray in color, that stood semicircle around his head doing nothing to help him, you hear Tiger say is he dead? Then they all walk out leaving him on the floor (only saw the feet shoes no faces but heard my other brothers voice) then Father Jeff walked into the room and knelt down beside him and blessed him, left with him still on the floor. RN nurse *short skinny thing with dirty blonde hair at shoulder length wearing dark blue scrubs and dark blue or black shoes) finally showed up pronounced him dead, she placed a call to firefighters to do lift assist, she proceeded to do documentation with him on the floor (I was getting livid that no one placed him back in bed or covered him up with a sheet) firefighters arrived placed him in the bed, they left, leaving only the RN and Jerry in the room, then the screen splits in half showing the bedroom and the outside of the house and it was total darkness with a street light reflecting on the cars parked out front of the house. A black hurst pulled up in front of the house, no one would move the cars to get gurney in to get Jerry and he said, “Can you believe he had to take “me out through the grass?” per Jerry said during this “movie”. Then the movie ended, and the room was empty of people. Just an empty bed with rumpled up sheets and a blanket at the foot of the bed partially hanging off onto the floor

Both he and I remained in the doorway to the bedroom and Jerry then proceeds to tell me Carol was there about 1 hour before and had left to go home because her dog and Tigers dog weren't getting along, he heard the doorbell ring and that hideous voice of hers talking to Tiger saying she wanted to come back and decided to board her dog and come back over since she lived over an hour away, Jerry said a few minutes later she came in the his room

He told me his cell phone had been taken away from him almost immediately moving into this house and he slept in his old recliner for weeks in the living room till hospice finally got him a bed.

Tiger had told him about Rob, he said Tiger had lied to him about me from the get-go. Telling him I hated him and Elaine, which was the furthest from the truth

Jerry proceeded to say with such sadness and anguish in his voice. All they wanted was his money, and that was it, he regretted calling him and not me in December of 2022. He asked if I saw him in my kitchen sitting on the floor leaning up on the cabinets, I told him yes and he scared the crap out of me, he laughed and apologized. I know you heard me tell you get your fat tail up and get to the courthouse now and get the will on March 13, 2023, he said I have tried to make it up to you threw music, the song Explosion, said did you hear me talking to you in it, told him yes I did, he said I meant it (*he said to me, "Mit, I'm sorry and Mit, I love you") and he said when you drove by Tigers house with Jen and the girls and saw my white truck in the driveway and your phone played Jewel's "Hands" the picture on your dash is me (him) I told him I know it is you, only one other person could see you.* him with darker hair and mustache and beard with aviator sunglasses) *** I have it on my phone

He then grabbed me with a big bear hug said "Don't cry please, I'm sorry but you needed to see what they hid from you, and lied to you about," then we stood in the archway of the kitchen and he said "You remember when you were 12 and Tiger was 24 he slammed your face into the windshield of my car and I kicked his ass for hurting you, I will be there and he won't ever hurt you again."

Then I was back in the same sitting position sorting clothes just as I was when I left. I was very uncertain as to what I had just experienced, I sat there getting nervous and put my hands on my face, my eyes and face were wet with tears.

I had been watching little house on the prairie "Sylvia" part 1 and it was almost over, This was mind blowing

The texture of his shirt, his scratchy beard on my forehead, his beard tangled in my hair, the grabbing of my hand with the warmth and physically feeling the doorway on my back as we stood there, the change of atmosphere (emotion and physical coldness in his room) the smell of chili. The anger I felt watching them leaving him on the floor and walking over him.

No way this was a lucid dream. I had not been thinking about Jerry or anything pertaining to Tiger either, and to literally feel the wetness on my face and eyes afterwards.

I had told Jenika my daughter about it and described the place and she said that was Tigers house my older brother who took him there and hid Jerry from me. I have never been to Tigers house in Schertz TX and with confirmation from Jenika that was it, but I had to confirm it myself and I found a video from the attorney that Tiger had submitted for evidence and Jerry is sitting on the side of the bed and in the back ground are the windows and roman cloth shades and his hair and beard was white in the video and he's asking why is SHE coming (Carol).

I also have the CCTV recording of the song Explosion by Ellie Gould, never heard of her or that song. That song started playing by itself on my cell phone and you can hear him saying "Mitzie I'm sorry" and later it says "Mitzie I love you".

I do not do much if anything with my phone, not tech savvy have to get grandkids to help me.

I have the photo of my brother Jerry's face on the dash of my car

I do not have a history of daydreaming and this movie shown to me was January 18, 2024

In mid-January 2023 I was driving home with Jenika and out of nowhere I was told someone was going to die on February 7, 2023, thinking it was my husband Rob and it being his birthday but it was my brother Jerry who was hidden from me by our oldest brother Tom (Tiger). On February 5, 2023 in late afternoon Jenika had received a text message from a friend of mine from childhood saying he was so sorry to hear of Elaines death on December 31, 2022 (Jerry's wife) I was never made aware of it so I called my older brother Tiger whom I thought I had a decent relationship with and asked him about it and was told I didn't need to know about and to let me know that Jerry was living with him and he had end stage ALS Lou Gehrigs disease and that was it, I had less than 48 hours to wrap my head around it all, did not get a chance to see him alive, Tiger s wife Jan called me that evening (6:38)pm to tell me Jerry died and is dead laying on the floor and then proceed to call me back three hours later asking if I want to come see him dead on the floor before the Mortuary takes him. Got all videos and photos

I openly admit that I have some absolutely bizarre experiences that cannot seem to be explained but this if something else beyond my comprehension. When the door open and the light appeared I was like I was not given a choice to go into it, almost like a vacuum effect if that makes sense. I can understand my out of body experiences I have had but this event and the others that followed are beyond grasp of comprehension in my feeble mind.

I was informed of things I had forgotten about or never had any knowledge of, it has filled in a lot of blank spaces over the last few years to be brutally honest. Having physical proof of the events is even more bizarre yet consoling to me that I haven't lost my mind.

Narrative B: Underground Realm Episode 2

Location of experience: Windcrest, Texas

Date: April 18, 2024 Time: between noon and 2:00 pm

I was in the den living room gathering porcelain figurines out of the large China cabinet and placing them on the sofa to be securely wrapped and packed into heavy duty black and yellow lidded tubs. Starting on the top shelf of larger figurines such as Virgin Mary and St. Michael and various angels and other religious items. Placed approximately 14 of them spread out on the sofa. I was seated in the middle of the sofa and watching TV as I started the 2nd batch, the TV is the far right corner of the room, big TV 55" on a cabinet, I was finishing up the bust of the Virgin Mary and leaned over to place her in the bottom of the tub, as I sat back up a huge slit of light from floor to ceiling and ceiling in here is at least 15" tall or more/

Opening larger than previous maybe 4-5" but it was more of an interior light coming through verses the sunshine. Now mind you. I was still in my long floral nightgown. I sat and really attempted to study this opening and again I was there (inside the door) before I knew it, the area was extremely cool and light flickering on the floor and walls of what I could see, the floor had a grainy feel under my feet (barefoot) I was compelled to wall down a wide corridor and could see torches affixed to the walls and not light bulbs. Seem like I walked a very long time with no windows or doors, just walls. I came upon a door thick old heavy wood with a heavy metal semi-circle handle I pulled it open and inside this room was a huge room wide and tall from what I could see I walked in and people where in there digging and moving dirt into piles at least 2-3 men per pile, I saw at least 8 piles of mounting dirt as I kept walking on the outer edge of the huge room but noticed there were no torches but actual electrical lighting, two men acknowledge me saying hello but not in English noticing they saw I was in my nightgown and not regular clothes and no shoes. That kind of scared me not knowing what they might do to me, I did step up my pace trying to find the door I had come in.

I see a man waving his hand at me beckoning me to come to him, I did but with caution, this man looked to be mid 50's gray wavy hair combed back with wire rim glasses a filthy white long sleeve shirt, he said, "Bonjour Madam," and rattled on in French and I could not understand the words as he spoke them, but in my head it was being translated to English. Said welcome, we have been waiting for your arrival, took me to a table with large paper maps spread open and asked that I sit down, and I did, he said the job was difficult, but the end would be fulfilling.

Said they were looking for a certain type of door buried below the current floor they were digging into, he said the door was tall half arc shaped wooden door and they had yet to locate it, was told I could help locate quickly. I told him I'm sorry, but I have no idea what you are

talking about and I had no clue where I was. He became somewhat flustered with my answer, asked me to wait as I waited for his return I kept looking around and watching all the activity in this huge room, I looked up to find a stunning dome ceiling with a gorgeous al fresco painting, then I knew my location, the man returned with an old gray bearded man wearing a dark brown robe and before any words spoken from anyone I studied his face and recognized him, the older man said Salve signora, again the translation in my head happening, he said it was so very nice to see you again and stated I would be the one that could help these gentlemen get their task completed more quickly, since I had already been shown the room.

I stood there with my mind racing trying to finish mentally pull files out of my memory cabinet that is deep in my mind, found it! Acknowledged the older man by his given name Salve. St. Benedict. He was the old man seated in a stone carved wall small library like room with arched doorways and shelf caved in to the stone filled with books and he was seated to the right at a very small table writing with an ink dipped pen on paper, in my earlier meeting with I was looking for a certain book and he said it was on the shelf in the back almost center and large, I was able to locate it and pulled it from the shelf and turning and placing the book on a waist high stone carved table or short wall about 5 feet long and 2-3 feet deep, the book hung over the edge of the table with its size, had no idea what book this was and how to begin to locate what I was looking for, he looked at me and I'm certain he saw the frustration coming over me and said go to page 12277 right side first column half way down (again in Italian).

I looked through the book to the page and location and saw my name handwritten in it. Had no clue why or what book I was looking at, I closed the book and placed it back on the shelf and I asked what book that with my name is, he didn't answer me right away and I was about to ask him again and he replied that is the "Book of Life" you have a place in heaven for you!

I was asking why they were so interested in finding that specific door, he stated do you know the vast secrets and treasures that being discovered here, look at this glorious room it had been hidden for hundreds of years with no one knowing about, I told him they knew about it but greed overcame their piety, I looked back at the map and the path or tunnel was not on it, I asked him to show me the small the library where I met St. Benedict, mind you St. Benedict was standing there and I looked at him and he knew I was extremely uncertain if I should reveal the location to that man, I was becoming so nervous and afraid that if I do reveal this door's location I will be betraying My Lord Jesus Christ. I continued to ask about the small library's location on the map, not on that map apparently, so he put up another map on the table and saw the library that was unmarked and I said nothing, figuring I would allow myself to have my prayer answered if I should proceed, St. Benedict asked me to come sit at a table a few feet away and where people had been eating and taking a break from the

work in the room, he reminded me that my name was in the book and it would never be removed, as I placed my right elbow on the table I glanced over and saw a newspaper with the date April 20, 1946! I told him regardless I'm still not comfortable revealing the site of the door, I told him to tell them where the door was and he just laughed and said I don't even know the location, I told him you do, and he said no I do not! I told him I saw the small library on the second map, but it was not in the huge room, the door was not too far from the library behind a stone carved rock wall, and the door would open and go down 23 steps to the right (room was not square but a circle shaped) and at the 23rd step the carved stones would need to be removed and would reveal what the world has been looking for centuries.

Both of us returned to the table and told the worker that I was uncertain if I should tell of its location to please be patient till my prayers are answered, he said "YES" they would wait. As I waited, I continued to survey the room and what look like a rectangular plinth raised up from the ground and statues, but the ceiling was just absolutely breath taking.

After what seemed to be hours, I felt comfortable knowing that my prayer was answered to show them the doorway that they were so desperate to locate, I showed them on the second map the exact location. He thanked me so graciously and hurried away while leaving myself and St Benedict together, we walked off towards the doorway I came through and he told me during that walk I was sent here for that specific reason and had it not been approved by the Almighty himself it would not have happened, he said your faith and trust in the Almighty is to be admired. He said The Almighty has bestowed upon you numerous gifts from birth along with your visions. He addressed me as Miriam, yes, you were there, never doubt your witnessing the crucifixion. Peace be with you, my friend! Were his departing words to me.

I was back seated where I had departed from, again baffled and my mind began to try to make sense of this journey, Why me? Looked around grab my smokes and sat therefore a bit, nothing had been done all the figurines still on the sofa and the Virgin Mary bust wrapped in the bottom of the tub as I had placed before I left. I guess I sat there maybe 10 minutes and had to get a coffee and I took and sat in the garden room the next room over where my small glass dining table was, drinking my coffee and replaying this in my mind, I spoke out loud to the Lord asking him why this is happening to me hoping to get an answer and I didn't at least I don't think I did. Found my notebook and started to jot it all down, and as I was writing it down the newspaper date April 20, 1946 why? Did I go back in time before my birth in 1964? I must have to have had 2 different languages of French and Italian spoken to me that I do not speak and yet it's being translated in my head for me to comprehend the conversations, my writing I have noticed it is almost like automatic if that could be understood, I'm just holding the pen and the words write by themselves, but did notice while writing this in the notebook seated at the table at the house on Windway and as I type this out (on my computer

in my new apartment) I see a pale peach color light above and to the sides of me that I can see in my peripheral vision, reminds me of the lights in my car at night that light of the door panels or a movie theater lights on the side of the chairs as you walk down the aisle. I have seen that peach-colored light before on different kinds of religious experiences? No clue what it is or why? Or better yet why me?

Narrative C: Green Labyrinth Episode 3

Location of experience: Windcrest, Texas

Time: About 11:11 AM to 11:55 AM

Date: May 5, 2024

While sitting in the garden room at the small dining table, looking through boxes of bric-a-brac and tossing out unwanted items, a flash of light caught my attention on the far wall, in the corner above a black shelving unit. I didn't see anything at first, but then out of nowhere, the doorway slit appeared. This time, I saw it coming down from the ceiling to the floor. Even though I was at least 15 feet away, it felt like I was standing right in front of it, despite being seated at the table.

Bright sunlight was streaming in from what looked like a forest area. I could see the blue sky through the branches and leaves of trees. The scene was beautiful and serene, with little green ferns curled like new blooms, old dried pine needles on the ground, and pine cones scattered around. I looked around and saw nothing but woods. I stood there, not knowing where to go, but I could hear birds chirping in the distance. I felt compelled to find the source of the chirping sounds, so I turned and started walking in that direction.

Suddenly, it was as if I ran into an invisible wall. I couldn't go any further in that direction. I reached out to see if I could feel the barrier; it was solid like glass but transparent. I turned to my right with my arms extended and took about four or five steps forward, only to encounter another barrier. I turned right again and continued walking with my arms extended, still in the wooded forest area. I could hear the birds chirping and saw little purple flowers blooming, along with a reddish-brown worm about eight inches long crawling on a small pile of leaves against a tree base. There were a few tall dome-shaped mushrooms that I had never seen growing in nature before. It reminded me of the places where gnomes might live in books I had read or pictures I had seen. I was actually enjoying being there; it was so peaceful and serene.

As I walked further, I could hear the sound of water, like a creek. When I ran into the barrier wall again, I didn't have my hands extended and literally ran into it with my body. I reached out to feel the barrier with my hands, which was cool to the touch and silky smooth. I couldn't feel the top edge of it. I started to get nervous, not knowing where I was going or how I would get out of this situation.

The wall took a sharp turn to the left and followed the ground level. I walked downward and could hear the water more clearly. I saw the water flowing on the other side of the barrier, but it wasn't on my side. I kept following the wall with my hand and walked a good distance until I finally reached a point where the creek water was on my side. I sat down on a smooth rock in the creek bed and watched the flowing water and the birds chirping in the trees. The rock I sat on was smooth, almost like the barrier wall. The water was cool and reflecting the sunlight.

As I got up from touching the water, my attention was drawn to a black suitcase with leaves, dirt, and stringy growth on it. It was wedged against a tree across the creek, as if it had been washed up and stuck. It piqued my curiosity, and I wanted to cross over and see what was inside. I tried stepping into the creek to get to the other side, but the barrier was there again, blocking my path. Frustrated, I went back and sat down, taking off my wet shoes and placing them beside me. I kept watching the suitcase and trying to figure out how to get to it.

Suddenly, a little dark-haired girl appeared out of nowhere, standing by the suitcase. She was wearing a white top with multicolored vertical lines and dark-colored shorts, with one sock on and no shoes. Her hair was mid-back length and slightly wavy. She looked to be about three or four years old. Her appearance was disheveled, and her skin was pale; she appeared to be a deceased child. She just stood there, looking back at me, her right hand sliding forward towards the edge of the suitcase. I thought that the child's body might be in the suitcase and that she wanted help being located.

Suddenly, I was back at the table in the garden room, seated in the same chair, with the boxes I had been sorting still there. My cell phone read 11:55 AM. I sat there for a moment, gathering my thoughts, then got up and grabbed a journal from the white stand. I jotted down what had happened. As I was writing, the identity of the child became clear: it was Lina Sadar Khil, who disappeared on December 20, 2021, from an apartment complex in San Antonio, TX.

At the time of her abduction, I was unaware of it. She appeared to me in a dream on December 27, 2021, and I started looking in local papers and news about a missing child, discovering that it was her. She has appeared to me a dozen times, showing me what happened to her and who took her. Rob and I decided to visit the complex in January 2022 and took random pictures that captured unbelievable images matching a drawing I had done a week prior. I have contacted the police numerous times to share my information, but it has fallen on deaf ears.

By the way, my journal with this episode was found in my bathroom late last night on a rolling cart, leaning next to a basket. There was no way I had placed it there, and no one else had either.

Narrative D: MY MOTHER REALM Episode 4

Location of experience: Windcrest, Texas

Event took place on July 5th, 2024, sitting at the table sorting through mail about 1:30 PM

This episode was almost 60 minutes long

Nothing unusual happening for the day adjusting to life in apartment paying bills

Again a tall slit of light from floor to ceiling appeared approximately 2 feet from my face while seated at the table with an opening about two to three inches wide with a warm light coming through but it did not go past the edge of the opening and within a blink of an eye I was in the opening standing on the sidewalk in front of my childhood home and watching my mother drive up in her car on the side of the house. She was walking in the grass towards me and I told her, "Where have you been it's been so long?", we hugged and kissed each other, and she looked at my arms and hands *full of blood bruising from bumping them. said you have thin skin like I do, I'm so sorry baby doll you got it from me, told her I put holy olive oil on them and seems to help the blood reabsorb more quickly

We walked to the front porch and sat down holding hands I could feel her wedding band between my fingers and the warmth and softness of the palms of her hands in mine. Looking at her face I could see a speck of mascara beneath her right eye, and I lifted her glasses up I did the spit removal that she used to do to us. She was wearing a white long sleeve sweater shirt black slacks and black boots. I could literally smell her perfume Called vanilla fields. I asked her where she had been that she had promised to come around me more often. She said she had been extremely busy, but she had never left my side. I asked her where daddy was she said doing his job and I told her I get Dimes and I know dad's with me and she just laughed, She told me to take my sunglasses off I put them on my head like usual. She said you need to color your hair too much Gray showing, but yet it mixes well with your hair and we both laughed, saw yellow jacket flying wasp around both of us and watched it till it flew away, I leaned back on my left palm and listened and a dried up purple berry from the Ligustrum tree had had made a painful imprint on the palm of my hand and brushed it off,

She told me she and daddy are so hurt by Tigers behavior and actions towards me with the dealings of Jerry and Elaines untimely death and legal procedures that I am currently dealing with. She proceeded to tell me that tiger has always been jealous of me being the only girl and the baby of the family. she thanked me for being a tiny terror and blossoming into such a wonderful young woman who could never say no to anyone that needed my help no matter what the cost.

She asked me if I knew when she was close to me and I replied yes, when I smell caress soap after a hot bath. I asked her if Jerry was with the her and dad and she said yes. She also said her and daddy we're with Jerry when he died and they both saw Jenika watching from above and what Carol did to Jerry and not to give up and prove that she murdered Jerry. But that I will be shown the way to do it. She proceeded to tell me that Jerry had so many regrets for his and Elaine's behavior, but it wasn't only our family but hers too, he said that Elaine started acting irrationally in the mid-90s and it scared him. He was afraid to ask for help he had thought it was from her alcohol consumption over the many years

She asked me if I remember tiger as a teenager drove directly into the telephone pole and knocked himself cocoo? I told her vaguely; I do you remember he seeing a doctor Langraby. She said that tiger has never been emotionally and physiologically right since then. he's a great liar and attempts to cover his tracks and that's what he continues to do today with you

She said Marjorie (her sister) was murdered by Bruce as we suspected and Carol knew about it and that's why her, Bruce and John packed up and move back to Australia so he wouldn't get caught and face the death penalty for his actions. She said Carol is dangerous and heed with caution, that she has serious mental issues that stem from early teen years. I looked down to the dirt beneath my feet behind the small cedar tree and could see a doodle bug crawling around in the dirt and a lovely breeze with a cooling sensation.

Mom asked if I recall driving to Corpus to see Fr. Ralph D'Orio in 1987 and I said yes I do because our neighbors Beverly and her daughter Steff followed us. Said do you remember after he walked down the church aisle blessing the congregation and you keeled over. She said I was blessed by the Holy Spirit and was given the gift of Prophecy and the following year you had that dream on the sofa and woke up so scared of seeing an airplane crash into a school, Lockerbee Scotland Pan Am flight 103, December 21, 1988. Also reminded me of another seeing my friend Michael shot on his college graduation night, a week before he died 1989. Then startled me by mentioning the sink hole premonition 2013 and it happened 2016 and the Uvalde shooting 2022, I asked her "How do you know about those?", she said, "I am with you all the time, Angel"). My mom died in 2002.

Do you remember Smitty's auction house you were 5 and chose a book Life and Times of Jesus Christ out of an entire box of children's book and Smitty gave it to me and she laughed saying and I thought you could read, but you memorized each page after she had read it to me.

We talked about a few things I can't mention, and said she would call me later and I hugged her and kissed her and said "I love you, mom, so much" and she told me "I love you, my Angel."

Then within a flash of a moment I was back sitting at my table again. This one was so fulfilling to me with seeing her and being able to hold her hands and the information she shared with me that I had no clue about, I was not sad but kind of asking myself what the hell is going on with me? I sat there and started to write everything she had told me, I knew it would be of importance sometime soon, then later on after jotting it all down, I went to change my clothes and when I pulled my tee shirt up over my face I smelled her Vanilla Fields perfume on my shirt and it is still there as I write this. still there after 3 weeks.